

Increase the visibility of your work – *DIGITAL PRESENCE CHECKLIST*

Welcome to “Your Open Science Journey”!

Connect your research to your data, software, institution, and more. Use this checklist to optimize your digital presence, increase discovery of your work to potential collaborators and partners, and receive credit when others use your work.

Target Audience

Primary: Team or project lead

Secondary: Team or project researcher

This checklist is generalized and will need to be adjusted based on your institution, lab, research team, and/or funder requirements.

A. YOU. YOUR ORCID

1. **Have your own ORCID.** It provides a persistent digital identifier that distinguishes you from other researchers and supports automated linkages between you and your research activities. Go here to register: <https://orcid.org>, and select “For Researchers”.
2. **Include your ORCID on all scholarly work.** This includes your publications, datasets, software, presentations, posters, signature block of your emails. Everything. This helps with linking to your ORCID profile.
3. **Keep your ORCID profile current.**
 - a. **Enable automatic updates** from Crossref and DataCite. [Digital Presence](#) blog post has the detailed steps.
 - b. **Set a reminder** every three months to ensure all your work is connected and current in your ORCID profile. Make sure your current affiliation and email are included and public for viewing. Add a second email (which can be private) to ensure account access should one become locked or no longer active.

B. YOUR PUBLICATIONS. THE DIGITAL OBJECT IDENTIFIER (DOI) + YOUR ORCID

1. **Include your ORCID as well as your co-authors ORCID on your publications.**
 - a. When given a choice, use journals that require your ORCID as well as your co-authors. In this way your paper will be registered along with your ORCID and automatically linked.
 - b. If your selected journal does not require ORCIDs, include it anyway. Place your ORCID as close to your name as possible. Also include the ORCIDs of your co-authors. Once determined, provide each team member a “cheat sheet” that includes a list of the team resources. Ensure each team member has access and is provided with any needed overview/training.

C. YOUR DATASETS. DOIs / PERSISTENT IDENTIFIERS (PIDs) + YOUR ORCID

1. **Select a repository that supports discovery and preferably is specific to your data type.** Consult [Repository Guidelines](#) for more information.

INCREASE THE VISIBILITY OF YOUR WORK

2. **Include your ORCID when you deposit your datasets.** And the ORCIDs of others who contributed to the dataset. If your selected repository does not require ORCIDs, include them anyway. Place ORCIDs as close to each contributor name as possible.
3. **Ensure the PIDs for related work are included – or added later.** This includes the DOI of your paper that cites this data, the PID of the software used to analyze this data, the PIDs of original datasets used to create aggregated data.
4. **Include documentation (i.e., metadata) with your dataset** in a README file or community recommended format.
5. **Include a license that is as open as possible.** <https://creativecommons.org/choose/>
6. **Cite your data in your publications.**

D. YOUR SOFTWARE. DOIs, GitHub + YOUR ORCID

1. **Preserve the version of software from your GitHub (or other development platform)** used for your research in a preservation repository such as Zenodo.
2. **Include your ORCID with the preserved version.** And the ORCIDs of others who contributed to the software.
If your selected repository does not require ORCIDs, include them anyway. Place ORCIDs as close to each contributor name as possible.
3. **Include a [Citation.CFF](#) and a [CodeMeta file](#)** (choose “Create” tab) for documentation with your software.
4. **Include a license** that is as open as possible. <https://choosealicense.com/>
5. **Cite your software in your publications.** Consult [Recognizing the value of software: a software citation guide](#) for more details.

References

Edmunds R, Specht A, Stall S, et al. (2022). Repository Guidelines. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6542494>

Katz DS, Chue Hong NP, Clark T, et al. (2021) Recognizing the value of software: a software citation guide [version 2; peer review: 2 approved]. F1000Research 2021, 9:1257
<https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.26932.2>

Quick Links to related checklists

- [Data Documentation and Citation Checklist](#)
- [Software Documentation and Citation Checklist](#)

To recommend updates, please email datahelp@agu.org. Include the name and DOI for the checklist in your email.

To cite this checklist: Stall, Shelley, Specht, Alison, Amato, Jennifer Gonçalves, Corrêa, Pedro Luiz Pizzigatti, Curivil, Francine Aparecida Lante, David, Romain, Erdmann, Christopher, Machicao, Jeaneth, Miyairi, Nobuko, Murayama, Yasuhiro, O'Brien, Margaret, Santos, Solange, Wyborn, Lesley, Vellenich, Danton Ferreira, & Mabile, Laurence. Digital Presence Checklist. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4706118>